

Artificial Neural Networks as Psychiatric Instrument

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Abstract. Artificial Intelligence (AI) has evolved enormously over the past decade and is being applied in ever more areas, psychiatry being no exception. AI envelops several modalities, one of which is Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), referring to computer models based on the workings of the brain. Despite already being described in the 50's, ANNs only became “mainstream” since the 2010's. The fact that ANNs find their inspiration in the workings of the brain raises the question whether they in turn can be used to model the (dys)functioning of the brain. This question has led to the rise of the field of “Computational Psychiatry”. This paper aims to provide an accessible introduction to ANNs, and illustrate how they can be applied in modern psychiatry.

The relatively young research field of Computational Psychiatry uses computer models to model processes inside the brain, and thus, moving beyond the symptoms (externally visible behavior), obtain better insight into the (internal, invisible) biological causes of neuropsychiatric phenomena. The aim is to be able to test hypotheses concerning how a certain neurological deficit can lead to a certain symptom, without having to intervene directly into the brain.

Artificial Neural Networks

One specific type of computer model, inspired by the functioning of the brain and applied for this purpose, is the *Artificial Neural Network* (ANN). The building block of an ANN is the *artificial neuron*: a mathematical construction that

receives several numbers as its input and performs a mathematical computation on these numbers to obtain an output value, or *activation*, which is then passed on as input to a following neuron. A connection between two neurons is defined by a *weight*, which determines how much of the activation of the first neuron is effectively passed on to the second one, and which can be either positive (excitatory) or negative (inhibitory). In essence, an ANN is a gigantic mathematical computation.

A simple type of ANN is the multilayered perceptron, in which neurons are grouped into three or more consecutive layers: an input layer, an output layer, and inbetween one or more so-called “hidden” layers (Figure 1). Each neuron from one layer is connected to each neuron from the following layer; there are no connections between neurons within a same layer. Information thus flows layer by layer, from input to output. The way in which neurons are combined (number of layers, number of neurons per layer, etc.) is called the model *architecture*.

Fig. 1. Schematic of a model constituted of multiple layers of neurons, whereby each neuron is connected to all neurons from the previous layer, but neurons within a same layer are not connected.

Applications of ANNs

ANNs have many applications, which can essentially be divided into two categories: *regression* and *classification*.

Regression is a task whereby the network typically only has a single output neuron, and needs to predict a numerical value (represented by the activation of this output neuron). E.g., the score a person would obtain tomorrow on a mood

questionnaire could be predicted by giving as input to an appropriate model the current score, a quantification of actual psychosocial stressors, and strength of the person's social network.

When performing classification, the goal is to associate with each input a correct label from a fixed set of labels. The network has as many output neurons as there are labels; each output neuron represents one label, and the numerical value (i.e., activation) of an output neuron is interpreted as the probability assigned by the network of the corresponding label being the correct one for the input under consideration. Consider, e.g., a collection of brain scans of patients with a neurocognitive disorder (ND) or depression in later life (DLL). An ANN could be constructed that takes as input the intensities of the voxels constituting the brain scans, and that has two output neurons, one representing ND, and the other representing DLL. The aim is such that when the network is presented with a brain scan, the correct corresponding output neuron becomes maximally activated.

How do ANNs learn?

ANNs can not learn autonomously; they need to be explicitly trained. During training, the weights of the network are adjusted such that its produced output comes closer to the desired output.

One approach to achieve this is through *supervised learning*, whereby a network is trained using a *training set*. Revisiting our previous ND/DLL-classifier, the training set would be a collection of brain scans for which the correct label is known. During the training phase, the network makes a prediction for each scan, which is compared to the correct answer. This information informs a complex mathematical process that attempts to update the weights of the model such that the prediction (i.e., the activations of the output neurons) better matches the correct answer. Once good results are obtained on the training set, the model can be applied to make predictions for scans of new patients for which no diagnosis has yet been made.

Another approach is *unsupervised learning*, whereby a large amount of data is presented to a model, and typically the aim is for the model to be able to internally cluster similar datapoints, which translates to these datapoints generating a similar network response. One example of such a type of model is a *self-organizing map* (SOM), in which an input layer is connected to a grid of output neurons in which each output neuron is connected to its neighbors (see Figure 2). The model is trained such that similar inputs (e.g., pictures of either a flower or a dog) largely activate the same cluster of output neurons, and the overlap between different neuron clusters is as small as possible.

With these concepts explained, in what follows we touch upon a few applications of the use of ANNs as model of the brain.

Fig. 2. Illustration of a self-organizing map. This hypothetical model is capable of distinguishing between pictures of flowers and pictures of dogs. Both types of pictures activate a different cluster of output neurons, with both clusters only having one common neuron.

ANNs as model of the human visual system

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), a type of ANN inspired by the human visual system, are commonly used for image analysis tasks such as the classification of images, object recognition (detecting and naming objects in a picture) or segmentation (color all pixels constituting a same entity in a picture). CNNs use filters that are moved across an input image (similar to the receptive fields of biological neurons in the visual system), whereby at each location the similarity between the filter and the underlying part of the image is determined, in order to extract representative features (e.g., edges). These filters are again organized in sequential layers (see Figure 3). Both in a number of popular CNNs as in the human visual system, the early layers exhibit sensitivities to simple geometric features (lines, edges, etc.), with properties becoming increasingly complex in deeper layers for ANNs, and deeper down the ventral temporal cortex for the visual system.

ANN model of prosopagnosia

Prosopagnosia is a condition that affects the ability of an individual to recognize faces, and that is linked to the *fusiform face area* (FFA) in the gyrus fusiformis. In order to model damage to the FFA, researchers trained a SOM to encode pictures of 4 (unique) faces, an elephant, and 5 (unique) objects into a 20x20 neuron grid. Subsequently, they trained a classifier that associated the output of the SOM with the correct label (“face 1”, “elephant”, etc.). The SOM managed to topologically separate the faces from the other classes. Following this, the artificial neurons encoding the faces were disabled, after which the classifier was

Fig. 3. Illustration of the convolutional mechanism of a CNN. The filters from layer 1 act on the input image. At each position, the match between the filter and the underlying part of the image is determined, resulting in a new pixel. The better the match, the darker the pixel. Each filter generates a new “image”, which is then subsequently scanned by the filters from the next layer.

no longer able to correctly “recognize” the faces, although the recognition of the other classes remained intact [5]. As such, this model represents a hypothesis concerning the biological cause of prosopagnosia.

ANN model of hallucinations

A pathogenetic hypothesis of auditory hallucinations in schizophrenia states that these are linked to excessive synaptic pruning during adolescence. In order to test this hypothesis, researchers used an ANN comprised of 4 layers: a 25-neuron input layer, a hidden layer, a 44-neuron output layer, and, crucially, a “memory”-layer [1]. Starting from a vocabulary consisting of 30 terms with which simple sentences could be formed, each term was associated with a vector of 25 numbers serving as network input, as well as a 43 number vector representing the desired network output for the corresponding term. The network was trained using 256 sentences that were presented word by word to the network, whose task it was to convert the input representations into the corresponding output representations. The hidden layer received as input a combination of the input layer and the memory layer, which contained a copy of the state of the hidden layer when processing the previous term. It was shown that the network managed to leverage the information from the memory layer to correctly identify the current term.

Subsequently, the network was tested with 23 consecutive sentences, each time separated by 5 ‘#’-symbols. The authors looked at how many words the

network converted correctly or wrongly, as well as how many times the network represented a word at its output when there was no input ('#'). This phenomenon was considered to be a hallucination. They also experimented with the breaking of network connections (as artificial analogue of pruning). The number of correct conversions diminished conditional on the number of pruned neurons from the input layer, but no hallucinations were observed. When the memory layer was pruned, however, at first this resulted in an improved conversion rate, but once the layer was excessively pruned the network started to “hallucinate”. This gives credence to the hypothetical association between synaptic pruning and hallucinations.

ANN model of Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD)

ASD can be associated with an excessive focus on details, whereby local patterns are picked up faster than global patterns. An ANN was used to test the hypothesis that this could be a consequence of an imbalance between excitatory and inhibitory neurons in the visual cortex [3]. The aim was to simulate the results of a behavioral experiment in which participants with and without ASD were shown an image of a large letter (global pattern) made up of a repetition of a small letter (local pattern), as shown in Figure 4a. Subsequently, participants were asked to name either the large or the small letter. Participants with ASD were faster to name the small letter, contrary to the control group.

The ANN was designed specifically to extract visual features, and consists of a succession of S- (“simple”) and C- (“complex”) layers. The S-layers detect simple patterns, that are processed into more complex features by the C-layers. Importantly, within an S-layer an inhibitory mechanism is at play, while the connections between the S- and C-layers are excitatory. Such a network was trained on images depicting digits of different sizes and at different positions (see Figure 4b). Following training, the network was presented with images depicting a large digit made up of repetitions of a smaller digit (Figure 4c). By manipulating the strength of the inhibitory and excitatory connections, the network could be brought to recognize either the large or the small digit. This reflects the contrast between neurotypical individuals (focus on global pattern) and individuals with ASD (focus on local pattern).

Limitations

There are several limitations to the use of ANNs as model of the brain. First, the number of neurons making up a typical modern ANN is many times smaller than those found in a human brain. Future studies will have to determine whether it is necessary to model the entire biological nervous system in order to study its mechanisms.

Second, the purely mathematical mechanism typically used to train ANNs is not present in the brain. Here as well, the question arises as to what extent the use of a different learning method foils the validity of the model; how exactly the

Fig. 4. Figurative illustration of: a. images used in the behavioral experiment; b. training set ANN; c. testing set ANN.

connection strengths between neurons came to be is less relevant than the final network configuration itself. What is relevant is that an ANN, once trained, does no longer learn, contrary to the brain. Worse still, when attempting to learn something new to a trained ANN, e.g., a new neuropsychiatric condition to classify, this will often result in so-called *catastrophic forgetting* [4], whereby previously learned information is lost. Another problem is that trained models typically do not generalize well to data that differs from that with which they were trained (e.g., an unseen species of dog or flower). Even worse, it is often possible to introduce tiny alterations to inputs that are invisible to the human eye (e.g., minuscule changes to certain pixels), but that make the network predict a specific *wrong* label. This phenomenon is known as *adversarial attacks* [4].

Conclusion

In this article, we tried to illustrate by way of some concrete examples what Artificial Neural Networks are and how they can be used to model mechanisms in the brain. We also indicated some limitations of this approach. Current knowledge and compute power do not yet make a model possible that encompasses the entire information processing in the brain, but with current techniques valuable results can already be obtained with respect to the testing of hypotheses regarding neuropsychiatric mechanisms. The potential of ANNs in neuropsychiatric practice is situated in different domains. We can think of decision support tools in diagnostics, whereby patterns in multimodal data (psychiatric, cognitive, affective, wearables, etc.) can be classified via an objective mechanism. Also in the domains of prevention and prognosis the appearance and evolution of deficits and symptoms can be predicted. Finally, ANNs could become an important tool for therapeutic purposes, e.g., to further develop *precision medicine* in order to be able to tailor treatment to individual patients.

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